

INTEGRATION OF INTERNET OF THINGS AND BLOCKCHAIN TO INCREASE HUMANITARIAN AID SUPPLY CHAINS PERFORMANCE

INTEGRACIÓN DE INTERNET DE LAS COSAS Y BLOCKCHAIN PARA AUMENTAR EL RENDIMIENTO DE LAS CADENAS DE SUMINISTRO DE AYUDA HUMANITARIA

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ABSTRACT:

This paper provide an overview of the benefits that the integration of IoT and Blockchain can produce on the Humanitarian Aid Supply Chain (HASC). Considering the large number of partner involved in HASC, traditional centralized information systems become very vulnerable. In the same sense, the lack of mutual knowledge obstruct the needed cooperation. The joint use of IoT and Blockchain can overcome these problems. Main benefit as well as barriers to this implementation is analyzed, considering the different phases of the HASC.

*Keywords*Covid19, Blockchain, Supply Chain Management, Internet of Things, Humanitarian Supply Chain

RESUMEN:

Este trabajo presenta una visión sobre los beneficios de la integración de Internet of Things (IoT) y Blockchain en la Gestión de la Cadena de Suministro Humanitaria (HSAC). Considerando el gran número de partes implicadas en la HASC, los sistemas de información centralizados tradicionales pueden ser vulnerables. En este sentido, uno de los problemas básicos es que la falta de una base común de conocimiento impide la necesaria cooperación en la cadena de suministro. El uso conjun

to de IoT y Blockchain puede ayudar a solucionar estos problemas. De este modo, el trabajo presenta los principales beneficios al igual que las principales barreras para la implantación de este tipo de sistemas descentralizados. El modelo de fases de la cadena de suministro es utilizado para identificar los impactos de la implantación conjunta.

Palabras clave: Covid19, Blockchain, Gestión de la Cadena de Suministro, Internet of Things, Cadena de Suministro Humanitaria

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1. INTRODUCTION

The different epidemics, outbreaks and pandemics occurred in this century (SARS outbreak 2002-2004, swine-flu pandemic 2009, Western African Ebola epidemic 2013-2016, among others) have increase the interest on supply chain security by receiving more attention from researchers focusing on different aspects related to the impact of specific actions in emergency situations. It also tries to ensure proper coordination with different government agencies by providing accurate and reliable information about the current situation and probable incoming crisis scenarios.

The relevance of Supply Chain Management (SCM) for improving business response capacity in the current pandemic situation has been highlighted by academia and professionals (1). Likewise, governments and other agents involved in global supply chains management, especially in the first Covid19 wave, soon realized that their internal procedures, traditional suppliers, contracting systems and preventive storage of material were not resilient enough to provide relief to their health and economic systems.

Global response to humanitarian crisis is largely based on the correct management of HASC. In emergency situations created during humanitarian disasters such as Covid19, different actors participate such as governmental authorities, international and local non-governmental organizations (NGOs), private companies, research institutions, army or other individual initiatives, among others. The coordination of all these actions, processes or goals directly influence the levels of responsiveness, flexibility or agility.

HASC is a field of study on the management of supply chains under extreme adverse conditions, which would normally not apply in commercial supply chain management (2). Among the characteristics that most differentiate HASC are the diversity of its members as well as the lack of trust and reliable information (2) which leads to significant coordination issues hindering adequate responses for local relief.

Given this scenario, integrating IoT devices with Blockchain technology offers a prolific prospect to dismiss several of the flaws in HASC Following (3) p55. "a blockchain can be considered a distributed database that is organised as a list of ordered blocks, where the committed blocks are immutable" This is an evolving technology. In this sense (4) have identify 4 technology waves. In blockchain 2.0 smart contracts were incorporated and develop it beyond cryptocurrencies. Blockchain 3.0 expand the applications in areas such as health and IoT. Finally, blockchain 4.0 is under development, and it should incorporate artificial intelligence. So, in the current blockchain 3.0, the combination of blockchain and IoT is grounded on decentralization in order to guarantee transparency, resiliency and security. Also, decentralization allows rerouting in case any information node becomes unavailable for any reason making possible the development of smart contracts which can state responsibilities for every deployed humanitarian action.

Although these technologies seem very promising, the implementation of Blockchain in the SCM is still, in most cases, in the testing phase or as proof of concept, with very little empirical evidence on the results of its implementation. In fact, some authors consider that the new hype of the moment can be treated as a silver bullet for most business problems. For this reason, both technical and organizational challenges must be taken into account for application in HASC.

This paper provides an overview of the benefits that the integration of IoT and Blockchain can produce on HASC performance conditions involving resources, processes, outputs, outcomes and impacts based on previous humanitarian emergencies models.

2. HUMANITARISM, COVID 19 AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

During pandemics, humanitarianism plays a fundamental role by encompassing different economic standardization, coordination, and constant monitoring of all actions is crucial to ensure supply chain resilience (5). In fact, flaws in these three issues drive to critical failures in achieving crucial milestones of humanitarian action due to delays, shortages of resources, duplicities or undersupplied areas. Different studies have analyzed diverse coordination mechanisms used when an increasing number of different entities play different humanitarian roles according to the flaws found in previous interventions related to an emergency response (6). Such mechanisms are mostly built on administrative and bureaucratic models and, in countless occasions, results rely on the skills of the staff involved (5). In many occasions, information exchange tend to be restricted to avoid inconsistencies or unreliability which may derive penal responsibilities (7).

The Covid19 crisis has brought out the relevance of SCM for relief interventions. The most relevant HASC distinctive features, especially for pandemics such as Covid19, are as follows:

- 1) Projections of demand in the initial stages require continuous adjusting due to the uncertainties derived from crucial variables of the pandemic which are initially unknown (rate of contagiousness, incubation period, degree of fatalities, etc.). Flexibility and agility become crucial priorities due to an extreme time pressure in a unceasing altering environment circumstances (2).
- 2) HASC design and maintenance need to be based on resiliency in order to assurance all essential streams of basic goods and information contemplating particular requirements regarding chain of cold, expiry dates, fragility, etc. (8).
- 3) HASC design must involve all different organizations and institutions to become actors in the pandemic relief (NGOs, Governmental and military bodies, volunteers, firms, etc.) when arranging and organizing resources assignment, agendas and goals to accomplish the projected outcomes (6).

Risks associated to HASC are classified as abnormal and normal risks (See among others (9)). Abnormal risks involve events basically related to natural disasters, war and terrorism, political instability and social and cultural grievances. Normal risks are mostly related to demand and supply deviations and tend to be much straightforwardly prevented and managed.

3. INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT) AND BLOCKCHAIN

The Internet of things enables numerous devices to remain permanently connected to the network and transmit data without interruption (10). In this way, a steady interaction with the environment is generated in order to have greater control over different

variables while minimizing risks and controlling possible deviations. It allows the interconnection of physical and virtual devices that can, in turn, interact with each other (11).

Centralized server/client models are at present the backbone of IoT systems. These centralized models have the benefit of controlling the information generated by the devices and having very energy-efficient clients, however, one of its major handicaps is the impossibility of flexibly exchanging data by the devices (12). The number of IoT devices is steadily growing, so that the effort for data management is increasing simultaneously, hindering scalability. In addition, centralized models enable data to be tampered with, which limits data reliability and leads to major security challenges (13).

Blockchain technology has the potential to overcome these difficulties since it is a distributed database that registers and saves all transactions between different members of a network. The integration of Blockchain technology with IoT will allow the process of collecting the information provided by the devices in a decentralized manner while reducing the costs associated with maintaining large data centers (14). The integration of IoT and blockchain is a main research topic, with a growing trend of publications (see (15) for a recent review)

Blockchain technology has been hyped as a “miracle” to a myriad of issues in different fields from industries to public sector. There is not a general agreement on the fact of considering this technology crucial in the nearest future or claiming that exaggerated expectations have been laid on Blockchain (16). In any case, Blockchain is developing a new paradigm in terms of trust in distributed information.

A Blockchain comprises two primary elements. The first is all the transactions made by the users of the system and the second is the Blocks in which transactions are recorded in the correct sequence and made sure they have not been manipulated (17). Hence, blockchain characteristics include:

- Ledger or database of transactions: Blockchain acts as a decentralized database to build a ledger formed by all the transactions registered.
- Immutability: Immutable ledgers are created through blocks of data in a way that once two parties have agreed to a transaction and recorded it, it can never be modified. This is achieved by replicating copies of the ledger in a distributed way throughout a large number of nodes and employing consensus mechanisms to ensure validity.
- Transactions are cryptographically secured using hashes and digital signatures to secure the chain.
- Decentralization: Blockchain is not free from scalability problems (18) and, in the actual technological state, isn't as scalable as the centralized alternative. But this issue is technologically affordable, while providing a high level of security. Latency can be decreased while solving the single point of failure problem that can occur in the centralized model.
- Anonymity: It is not a compulsory characteristic of blockchain, but it can be implemented if it is considered an interesting feature. In this sense, blockchain implementation allow for different level of anonymity (19) So, if anonymity is a desirable feature, blockchain can ensure it. On the other hand, if anonymity is not desirable, blockchain can be implemented to avoid it.
- Improved security: the possibility to tamper with the ledger is very costly or resource intensive and there is no single point of failure that can shut down the whole network.
- Increasing capacity: by increasing the number of nodes that replicate the ledger throughout the network.

Blockchain is a mechanism of collective action between people or entities that do not necessarily trust each other but all of them have a common goal (20). Until now trust has been managed by institutions, however blockchain allows the existence of trust without any institution controlling it as participants place their trust in the system and not in a particular individual. Contrary to institutions which require large number of officials and a complex bureaucracy to ensure that participants comply with the rules of a system, a Blockchain employs an algorithm-based and machine-executed consensus protocol for this. Furthermore, contrary to bureaucratic institutions which are always susceptible to hijacking by persons involved in them, a Blockchain-coordinated system has a transparent and prohibitive cost for its hijacking (e.g., controlling more than half of the processing power of all nodes).

It is especially useful to generate trust among unknown suppliers, customers and/or service providers. SCM requires a coordination of multiple parties, processes and assets needed and the resolution of disputes is expensive (8). Historically, there have been a lot of different ways to ensure trust in such settings – trade agreements, letters of credit and export insurance are only some examples that aim to accomplish this.

Blockchain can prove authenticity and ownership as well as save time in those cases in which multiple serial steps of paperwork slow things down such as supply trade documentation, supply chain finance, etc (20). Other Blockchain applications are those ensuring trust in recalls, chain of custody tracking, provenance, auditability or fraud and data tampering situations. This can be of particular

importance in the context of emergency scenarios such as the Covid-19 pandemic, which require the immediate collaboration between various actors that do not know and necessarily trust themselves a priori.

Some of the main challenges in supply chain are data visibility, process optimization and demand management (21). The combination of IoT and Blockchain requires a definition of standards aiming to improve IoT interfaces and scenarios with the Blockchain. Low-cost, disposable and reusable devices can be applied for real-time tracking and alerts for monitoring temperature and humidity in cold chains for pharmaceuticals and food while integrating supply chain solutions (22).

Although blockchain can build trust by itself, when smart contracts are incorporated, the trust in Blockchain is reinforced. Smart contracts can be defined by means of a series of milestones that need to be fulfilled so that contracts are completely satisfied (23). Milestones can be double checked through IoT at the delivery stage right before transportation by fulfilling requirements like characteristics, quantities, reception, temperature, storage, etc. During transportation, milestones like time, movements, maintenance of pressure and temperature conditions, etc. can be controlled. Finally, at the reception of the products the milestones to be met would be for example distribution conditions, carrier data, etcetera.

For HASC in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, the implementation of Blockchain with IoT implies location awareness, self-reporting, auto correcting and interoperability. HASC goals involve increasing speed and flexibility, improving visibility as well as self-optimizing and self-orchestrating (17). This is where the application of Blockchain with IoT can support technologies digitization, data standards, interconnectivity, global scaling and applied intelligence (24).

4. A MODEL FOR BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT IMPLEMENTATION IN HASC

Communication and collaboration within the different organizations involved in the HASC are crucial for efficiency and effectivity in Covid-19 pandemic management. Some of the uses identified for Blockchain and IoT to integrate internal and external infrastructural support of independent humanitarian actions in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic are (25):

- Payments management: Current payment systems involve various intermediaries. Customer fees, and prolonged bureaucratic assignments especially when dealing with banking systems from different countries or economics areas. Blockchain and IoT allow instant payments as financial institutions gain visibility and control of all transactions performed by the different HASC actors. Transaction costs would decrease dramatically while tampering risks become insignificant while increasing trust. This doesn't mean that blockchain will replace actual payment system such as TARGET, but it will complement it by downsizing the transaction cost as well as enhancing trust. Fintech is a developing business model working on this road.
- Humanitarian actions control: Blockchain and IoT technology allow ex-ante and ex-post control of cluttered humanitarian actions as continuous resources auditing will enhance last-time difficulties resolution capabilities. Blockchain is specifically well suited for tracking information and making it visible to all parties to provide online response to changes in demands.
- Monitor and correct inefficiencies: Blockchain and IoT technologies generate a broad range of possibilities to correct inaccurate and/or inefficient actions and outcomes by keeping a constant ledger of transactions available for all actors that can improve progress on accounting and auditing of humanitarian actions and performance.
- Compliance enforcing: For the HASC to accomplish humanitarian goals and perform optimally, resources such as food, pharmaceuticals or other basic goods need to be in the disaster zone at the right time. Blockchain and IoT enable online visibility of data so goods shipping can be monitored and controlled according to compliance regulations.
- Cryptographic security of identities: Different real identities can be associated with cryptographic identities through Blockchain. This can be especially useful to protect personal data of victims and injured individuals as well as properties to avoid duplication efforts when identifying resources, actions or people enabling encrypted updates according to the evolution of the disaster. Although this issue could also have a negative side, regarding the difficulty to identify real identities behind money laundry or even terrorist financing.

Blockchain and IoT technologies have the potential to improve speed, security, transparency or efficiency, among other features, within HASC. Hence, these technologies can move HASC in a Covid-19 world to a higher-level following (26) who described four levels of supply chain information integration from internal linking across functions and processes, for information sharing with customers and vendors to information synchronization among multiple supply chain partners.

This paper suggests an integrated model for HASC that intends to overcome issues such as lack of online data access, inconsistency in data formats or tampered information (13). We can differentiate several phases in the implementation of these technologies in Covid-19 relief management. During the first phase, Blockchain and IoT are applied only to ensure the supply in good conditions of food,

medicines and other basic necessities such as personal protective equipment (PPE). In a second phase, other resources for pandemic management (e.g., tests) are also included. In the third phase we consider the transfer of infected and the census of the healed and deceased will be added to the system.

These phases involve distributed applications or DApps as well as Web browser access to verify traceability of goods sent to catastrophic zones (16). This is feasible considering Blockchain resilience to disruption as information is distributed and therefore local computer or network failure (or compromising) does not lead to a data loss or manipulation (27).

Blockchain and IoT can provide resilience for all infrastructures necessary to provide relief (fire and police services, first responders, hospitals, municipalities and local governments, etc.) which may have their local computer systems unavailable (28). In fact, within the Supply Chain, all entities involved could know first-hand which systems are still working and which ones are not. Information regarding what is available and where like the state of warehouses, location of trucks and cargo is basic for starting HASC deployment (29). As all information is online and trustful, retargeting in case of changing conditions (e.g., infections emerging in a different area) is much more fluent and faster while risks of failure are minimized.

After disaster actions sometimes are even more important than actions performed during the disaster (30). This also applies to the Covid-19 pandemic. Supplies of medicines and basic nourishment products such as milk or even water need to be guaranteed for survivors. Same applies for scarce medical supplies such as PPE and even complex apparatus such as respirators or extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) machines. Blockchain and IoT can help to determine which closest warehouses can be accessed to maintain flows of such goods and for how long to optimize new orders to providers and rerouting in case of need (31). In addition, medicine distribution can benefit from these technologies by ensuring that food reaches the most needed victims through smartphone camera eyeball identification avoiding bad actors taking advantage of the chaos and getting more than their fair share or pretending to be victims.

This integrated model can be applied to exogenous and endogenous disasters. Exogenous disasters are those in which one section of the community suffers biological, economic and psychosocial distress while other section of the community profits from material gains and social satisfaction (32). Endogenous disasters refer to events leading to severe danger, injury and destruction, or disruption of the social structure and essential function of the society.

According to UN/ISDR (2002), disaster management involves five generic stages for which, under adaptation for Covid-19 scenarios the following benefits from Blockchain and IoT implementation can be observed:

- (1) During the Prediction stage, mitigation and preparedness activities are deployed by incorporating all structural measures focused on limiting the potential adverse impact of a pandemic and natural hazards, environmental degradation and technological hazards that can emerge from lockdown measures. An example can be limited mountain rescue activities or interrupted monitoring of natural hazards (e.g. floods due to dams breaking) as a side effect of lockdown measures. Blockchain can also facilitate the creation of “decentralized humanitarian autonomous organizations” to improve cooperation on collective trust (33). Non-structural measures are also implemented to ensure a fast and effective response in case of emergency such as early warnings for rapid temporary evacuation or quarantining of people in threatened locations. Blockchain can help automate regulatory compliance requirements on safety as well as eliminate duplication efforts in identification processes while permitting encrypted updates of evacuates in real-time. Factom (34) create a immutable audit trail that allow for updating documents and can be an example to automete regulatory requirements.
- (2) Warning. During this stage detailed and accurate information is provided timely to all individuals in order to guide and help them to take correct actions to minimize risks and response effectively. Individuals need to know that information comes from a trusted source. Blockchain with IoT can help to ensure on one hand, that the information comes from identified institutions and, on the other hand, that data provided is sent by identified IoT device (14). For example, Blockverify (34) used blockchain to verify information accuracy in the pharmaceutical chain, which is of direct application to HASC.
- (3) Emergency relief. Direct intervention once the pandemic and corresponding lockdown measures are known to happen or to be happening takes part at this stage. Life preservation and subsistence of victims are the main focus during this stage that may take days or months for patients that develop Covid-19 Smart contracts are scripts stored in the blockchain that improve operational efficiency. They provide security and integrity for IoT data. They are crucial in this stage to achieve fast and accurate relief (14). (35) present an application to ensure blood donation supply traceability that is relevant in this vein.
- (4) Rehabilitation. After the pandemic wave subsides numerous decisions and actions need to be taken to restore living conditions previous to it. Also, different risks may appear when the environment has been modified so prevention measures are crucial at this stage. Blockchain is able at this stage to secure identities and clinical data of victims and reduce fraud in activities while optimizing HASC (36). UniquID, ShoCard of SolidX (34) are example of who blockchain can be used in this sense.

(5) Reconstruction. This stage involves all structural and non-structural actions commenced to threshold the impacts of natural hazards, environmental degradation and technological hazards as well as all efforts to restore the living conditions previous to the pandemic. In this context, automated validation of claims can be performed through Blockchain increasing the security and efficiency of the process (37). This way, real-time automatic claims processing, eligibility verification, and preauthorization could turn into a reality. In addition, and with applicable consents, researchers could access to different subsets of the stored data for research. In this stage, issues such as piracy prevention, completion of the chain of custody and establishment of a perimeter of trust can benefit dramatically from Blockchain and IoT implementation.

Along with all these advantages of joint implementation of IoT and Blockchain in HASC, it needs to be outlined that technology evolution involves high levels of uncertainty due to the lack of standards (4). This means that the perceived benefits may not offset the associated risk in many cases. In this sense, (38) found that integrating IoT across various supply chains is still a crucial challenge. This fact is especially significant in the case of HASC, since the diversity of organizations and agents involved in emergency situations hinders supply chain technology integration. For blockchain implementation in supply chains, studies such as (39) have determined that, at present, there are still major barriers such as regulatory uncertainty, lack of knowledge and high sustainability costs. Therefore, the rapid implementation of IoT and blockchain in HASC is conditioned on the technology absorption capacity of the different HASC network central nodes, especially government agencies and pharmaceutical companies which take a central role in fast emergency relief. Hence, mitigating the risks associated with novel technologies require regulatory frameworks that ensure a secure deployment of all the blockchain and IoT potential.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Hence, this study conceptualizes the disaster management and HASC under the perspective of the implementation of Blockchain and IoT by outlining potential applications. Considering, the large number of parties involved in HASC, together with its diversity (national and local governments, international organizations, companies, NGOs, ...) traditional centralized information systems become very vulnerable. In the same sense, the lack of mutual knowledge obstructs the development and implementation of information and communication systems that can guarantee transparency, reliability, security and process integrity. The joint use of IoT and Blockchain can overcome these. In fact, the lessons learned from the first stages of Covid-19 crisis points in this direction.

Moreover, both technologies offer plenty of opportunities of scalability and security under a cost-effectiveness perspective. As a result, IoT allows through affordable devices to collect plenty of information from the environment that can result in major advancements in life saving and restoration of living conditions previous to the disaster. This means that for HASC a gradual implementation process needs to be developed, starting with those challenges with highest cost-benefit ratio considering technology evolution when applied to warehouse management, traceability and tracking (40). It doesn't mean that IoT and Blockchain will solve all HASC problems. In fact Covid-19 has proved the large number errors and highlighted the different criteria that underline the HASC implementation in different countries. Even more HASC is sometimes under pressure of corruption in many situations. In this sense, IoT and Blockchain can help in developing trust and cooperation, creating transparency, but could not solve the whole problem, which should need a broader redefinition of HASC. In addition, future lines of research should focus on the development of optimal platforms to implement them in HASC or regulatory policies to ensure an optimal implementation of these technologies.

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